

Excursions in Solid State Chemistry[†]

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Some highlights of the author's research investigations over the last three decades in the area of solid state chemistry are briefly presented. The aspects covered include examples from studies related to synthetic strategies, phase transitions, novel solids, new techniques as well as electronic and magnetic properties of oxides. High temperature oxide superconductors are discussed in some detail in view of the great excitement they have caused in the last few months.

CHEMISTS have contributed to the study of solids since the early beginnings, but it is only recently that solid state chemistry is getting to be recognised as part of mainstream chemistry. Chemists by virtue of their understanding of structure and bonding as well as their inherent synthetic abilities are able to make unique contributions to the study of solids¹⁻³. Tailor-making solids of desired properties is becoming possible only because of the advances made in solid state chemistry in the last few years¹⁻³. Solid state chemistry mainly deals with the synthesis, structure, properties and reactivity of solids, all these aspects being relevant to materials design.

I have been working in solid state chemistry for the past three decades and have tried to contribute to the various facets of development of the subject. The different aspects of the subject that my coworkers and I have contributed to, cover novel synthetic strategies, defect ionic solids, phase transitions, structure-property relations, solid surfaces, new phenomena and new techniques. We have employed several of the emerging techniques such as MASNMR, EXAFS, electron spectroscopies and HR electron microscopy in our studies. In the area of defect solids, we have been specially interested in the creation and migration of defects. It was my intention to present some of the highlights of our recent investigations in solid state chemistry. I have now decided to be very brief in covering these aspects because of the exciting development of high-temperature oxide superconductors which has become the talk of the town since January 1987. I consider myself fortunate to have been able to participate in research on oxide superconductors and I would like to take this opportunity to present some of our important findings. It has been a most enjoyable and thrilling experience to belong to such a period of excitement in solid state science, unprecedented in recent times. What is specially rewarding to me is the fact that I have been working for some years on the solid state

chemistry of certain oxide systems which have gained much importance since January 1987 because of high-temperature superconductivity. It is noteworthy that superconductivity has really moved into the domain of chemistry, since the chemistry of these oxides has much to do with their superconducting property.

Some highlights in solid state chemistry :

Synthesis : Several strategies have been developed to synthesise a variety of complex metal oxides, sulphides and other substances by employing ingenious means. A wide range of conditions including high pressures, high temperatures, electron or laser beam irradiation and ultrafast quenching have been employed for the purpose^{4,5}. A specially noteworthy method of preparing solids at relatively low temperatures is the precursor method⁶. The precursors can be solid solutions containing the desired cations in the desired proportion or well-defined compounds. The precursor on decomposition, reduction or any other transformation gives a homogeneous monophasic product. Several precursor solid solutions including carbonates, hydroxides, oxalates, cyanides, nitrates and sulphides have been employed by us to prepare unusual solids, some even metastable. The carbonate solid solutions are specially useful, since a number of metal carbonates crystallise in the calcite structure. For example, starting from solid solutions of the type $\text{Ca}_{1-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{CO}_3$, a number of oxides in the Ca-Mn-O system have been prepared. Unusual oxides of the type $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{O}_6$ possessing ordered octahedral, tetrahedral and square-pyramidal coordinations of Fe/Mn ions (or ordered oxygen vacancies) can only be prepared from the topochemical reduction of the perovskite oxide $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x\text{O}_6$ (Fig. 1) which in turn is prepared by the decomposition of the carbonate solid solution $\text{Ca}_2\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{Mn}_x(\text{CO}_3)_4$. A one-step synthesis of monophasic Chevrel phases, $\text{M}_x\text{Mo}_6\text{S}_8$, has been devised in our laboratory⁹ by the reduction of the precursor thiomolybdate, $\text{M}_x(\text{NH}_4)_y\text{Mo}_6\text{S}_9$.

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Fig. 1. Topochemical reduction of the perovskite I gives the ordered defect (oxygen vacancy) structure IV with square-pyramidal, octahedral and tetrahedral (SP, O, T) coordinations of the transition metal ions. Heating IV in vacuum transforms it to the brown millerite structure (BM).

Topotactic or topochemical reactions can yield unusual, often metastable, solids. Intercalation chemistry generally involves topochemical reactions. We have recently prepared cubic MoO_3 (of ReO_3 -type structure) as well as the cubic solid solutions, $Mo_{1-x}W_xO_3$ by the dehydration of their monohydrates⁹. Having prepared $Mo_{1-x}W_xO_3$, we have studied the shear planes formed by the oxygen-deficient solid solutions. We have also synthesised several bronzes of the type $K_yMo_{1-x}W_xO_3$ by employing a low-temperature solid state reaction between the oxide and the alkali metal iodide; titration of the iodine liberated directly gives the amount of alkali metal intercalated. We have also prepared layered alkali metal bronzes of MoO_3 by this method. Topochemical reduction of $LaNiO_3$ yields $La_2Ni_2O_5$ with interesting coordination of Ni^{2+} ions¹⁰; $La_2Ni_2O_5$ cannot be prepared starting from La_2O_3 and NiO or any other way.

The sol-gel route has provided an excellent means of preparing various solids by a low-temperature route¹¹. We have employed the sol-gel method to prepare composites of metal particles with metal oxides (e.g. Ni- Al_2O_3). This has provided a means of investigating clusters of metal particles¹².

Phase transitions: Studies of phase transitions of solids involving changes in crystal structure and properties are of great interest. We have investigated various types of phase transitions in metal halides, oxides and so on for the past several years^{13,14}, of special interest being the transformations accompanied by changes in electronic and magnetic properties. Phase transitions involving changes in spin states of transition metal ions^{13,15} are most interesting and we are continuing to study these transitions in transition metal oxides and complexes. We have

also been interested in the origin of long-period structures such as the polytypes¹⁶. In the last four years, we have got deeply interested in the computer simulation of phase transitions of solids by employing the generalised Monte Carlo method incorporating variable shape and size of the simulation cell^{17,18}. We have successfully simulated the phase transitions of CCl_4 and adamantane by this method (Fig. 2). We have also simulated the glassy states of molecular and hydrogen bonded substances (isopentane and water)^{19,20}. Computer simulation employing the Monte Carlo and molecular dynamics methods will undoubtedly be of great value in predicting crystal structures, solid state reactions and in deriving good potentials.

Novel solids: Some unusual solids such as $Ca_2Fe_{2-x}Mn_xO_6$, $La_2Ni_2O_5$ and cubic MoO_3 investigated in this laboratory were referred to earlier. I would like to specially draw attention to the new class of solids involving the intergrowth of two or more related solids. Recurrent intergrowth structures where two solids intergrow in an ordered fashion at the unit cell level, often generating homology, are indeed fascinating. Many such solids have been recently described and the origin of long-range order in intergrowth structures examined^{21,22}. One of the best examples of recurrent intergrowth structures is provided by the homologous series $Bi_4A_{2n-1}B_{2n+1}O_{6n+9}$ formed by the oxides of Aurivillius family, $(Bi_2O_2)^{2+}(A_{m-1}B_mO_{3m+1})^{2-}$. Long-range elastic forces seem to be important in forming such intergrowths (Fig. 3). Recently, intergrowths of the type $La_{n+1}Ni_nO_{8n+1}$ (e.g. $La_3Ni_2O_7$, $La_4Ni_3O_{10}$) have been synthesised and characterised²³. It should be remarked that disordered intergrowth itself is of common occurrence in metal oxide chemistry, and

many complex metal oxides show occasional presence of other oxides (one or two unit-cell width) of different compositions. The phenomenon of intergrowth may provide a means of tuning or altering properties of solids and this aspect needs to be investigated.

Fig. 2. Computer simulation of the phase transition in adamantane involving molecular orientation.

New emerging techniques of characterisation : It is increasingly becoming necessary to employ better and newer techniques of characterisation to investigate solids. Thus, without high-resolution electron microscopy, it is not possible to study the local structure or the ultramicro-structure of solids. We have employed a variety of structural and spectroscopic tools to investigate several problems in the chemistry of metal oxides and other systems. For example, we have used electron energy loss spectroscopy (in an electron microscope) to study the electronic structure of transition metal oxides²⁴. EXAFS has been employed to examine important catalysts such as Cu-ZnO (methanol synthesis) and Co-Mo-Al₂O₃ (hydrodesulphurisation)^{25,26}. In case of the Cu-ZnO catalyst, two types of Cu²⁺ have been identified besides Cu⁰, just as in Co-Mo-Al₂O₃, two types Co species have been

found to occur. We have developed a technique to determine the number of *d*-electron states in metal oxides and other solids by employing Auger electron spectroscopy²⁷. The technique is useful to study catalysts, surface oxidation of metals and so on. In addition, photoelectron spectroscopy has been employed by us to study electron states of solids and surfaces, and a number of problems of interest in solid state chemistry has been solved²⁷. In recent months, we have employed multinuclear solid state NMR to investigate glasses and phase transitions²⁸. Photoacoustic spectroscopy has been exploited to study many interesting problems in solid state chemistry, especially phase transitions²⁹.

Properties and their relation to structure : Studies directed towards the unified understanding of the electronic and magnetic properties of transition metal oxides of perovskite, K₂NiF₄ and other structures have been a major preoccupation in this laboratory^{2,14,30}. Accordingly, we have investigated the electronic and magnetic properties of several series of oxides of the ABO₃ type³¹, where A=La-Lu and B=Ti-Cu. Similarly, oxides of the K₂NiF₄ structure such as La₂NiO₄ and La₂CuO₄ have been studied in detail³². We have also carried out an extensive comparative study of the electronic and magnetic properties of oxides of K₂NiF₄ structure and their three-dimensional analogues³³. It appears that the quasi two-dimensional oxides never become truly metallic or ferromagnetic. Another important area which we have worked in relates to metal-nonmetal transitions in binary and ternary metal oxides. One of the oxide systems which shows an interesting localised to collective *d*-electron transitions is LnCoO₃ (Ln=La-Lu); we have studied this transition by ⁵⁷Co Mössbauer spectroscopy and other techniques³⁴. La₂NiO₄ undergoes a metal-nonmetal transition only in two dimensions (*ab*-plane)³⁵; it also shows anti-ferromagnetic ordering at 200 K. Ln_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ becomes progressively ferromagnetic and metallic with increase in *x*³⁶. Compositionally controlled metal-nonmetal transitions are specially interesting, a typical system exhibiting the phenomenon being LaNi_{1-x}M_xO₃, where M=Cr, Mn, Fe etc. (Fig. 4); with increase in *x*, the material becomes an insulator, while at *x*=0 it is metallic³⁷. In all such oxide systems where the temperature coefficient of resistance changes sign (from metallic to nonmetallic behaviour) at some critical composition, we find that the value of conductivity universally corresponds to Mott's minimum metallic conductivity (10²-10³ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹). This is indeed an important observation that needs to be explained. We have been generally interested in metallicity of substances³⁸ and in developing criteria for metallicity. A simple thermodynamic criterion based on the latent heat of vapourisation has been found to distinguish the metallic elements from the non-metallic ones³⁹. In the last few months, I have engaged myself in intense research in the superconducting oxides, since many of them belong to oxide families with which I have been so familiar

Fig. 3. High resolution electron microscopic image of the recurrent intergrowth in $\text{Bi}_2\text{Ti}_2\text{CrO}_{10}$. Intergrowth of $n=3$ and 4 members of the Aurivillius family can be seen. Computer-simulated image and structural projection are shown.

Fig. 4. Resistivity data of $\text{LaNi}_{1-x}\text{M}_x\text{O}_4$ showing compositionally controlled metal insulator transition. Notice that the resistivity value when TCR changes sign corresponds to Mott's minimum metallic conductivity.

for some years. In the next section, I shall briefly review some of the important results obtained by us on high-temperature oxide superconductors.

High-temperature oxide superconductors :

The discovery of superconductivity around 30 K in the La-Ba-Cu-O system by Bednorz and Müller⁴⁰ in 1986, gave great impetus to superconductivity research. It was soon found (in January 1987) that the oxides of the La-Ba(Sr)-Cu-O system exhibiting high T_c in the 30-40 K region possessed the K_2NiF_4 structure⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ (Fig. 5). This was followed by the more exciting discovery of superconductivity above the liquid nitrogen temperature in the Y-Ba-Cu-O system⁴⁵. Because of the high T_c superconductivity, many oxide systems, including some old ones such as La_2CuO_4 , are now being investigated by a large number of workers all over the world. I shall briefly present here some of the important studies carried out in this laboratory since January 1987.

Oxides of K_2NiF_4 structure : As early as 1973, we published a study⁴⁶ of the properties of La_2CuO_4 . Of special interest is the magnetic susceptibility anomaly⁴⁷ found around 220 K. The susceptibility maximum is field-sensitive and arises from antiferromagnetic ordering. It is heartening that such ordering has been confirmed by recent investigations⁴⁸. We have investigated superconductivity in several oxides in the La-Ba(Sr)-Cu-O system; it is now known that La_2CuO_4 and $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{CuO}_4$ are also superconducting. Resistivity behaviour of $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x(\text{Ba}_x)\text{CuO}_4$ reveals an important feature of these oxides in the normal state. They exhibit

Fig. b. The K_2NiF_4 structure. Position of A, B and oxygen in A_2BO_4 are shown.

resistivities in the 10^{-2} – 10^{-3} Ω cm range (Fig. 6) which are close to the 'minimum metallic conductivity' value of Mott. Many of the oxides of the general formula $(La_{1-y}Ln_y)_{2-x}Sr_x(Ba_x)CuO_4$, where $Ln=Pr, Nd, Eu$ or Gd , exhibit superconductivity in the 15–40 K region^{49,50}. These oxides show maximum T_c around a specific value of x (or the nominal Cu^{3+}/Cu^{2+} ratio) suggesting the presence of strong correlation; it is possible that T_c is proportional to the energy scale of the antiferromagnetic fluctuations⁵¹. It is interesting that T_c in these oxides of K_2NiF_4 structure shows a maximum around a critical unit cell a parameter (3.78 Å) as well. These oxides also undergo a tetragonal–orthorhombic distortion before the superconducting transition.

$La_{2-x}Ba_{3+x}Cu_6O_{14}$ and related systems: Soon after we initiated studies of the superconductivity of $La_{2-x}Sr_x(Ba_x)CuO_4$ and related oxides, we parallelly examined^{50,52} the electrical properties of $La_4BaCu_5O_{13}$, $La_3Ba_3Cu_4O_{14}$ and $La_{2-x}Ba_{3+x}Cu_6O_{14}$. $La_4BaCu_5O_{13}$ is a low resistivity oxide which does not show superconductivity. We have found a superconducting transition in $La_{2.5}Ba_{3.5}Cu_6O_{14}$ and its analogues around 40 K. Heating such oxides in oxygen at low temperatures increases the transition temperatures of this family of oxides.

Fig. 6. Resistivity behaviour of $La_{2-x}Sr_xCuO_4$. Data of $La_2Li_{0.1}Cu_{0.9}O_4$ is also shown. Oxygen-excess La_2CuO_4 and La-deficient La_2CuO_4 are also superconductors with $T_c \approx 40$ K.

$Y-Ba-Cu-O$ and related systems: Since Y_2CuO_4 was not known to crystallise in the K_2NiF_4 structure, we initiated a study on compositions of the type $Y_{2-x}Ba_{3+x}Cu_6O_{14}$ analogous to $La_{2-x}Ba_{3+x}Cu_6O_{14}$ described by Er-Rakho *et al.*⁵³. Although compositions of these yttrium oxides are bi-(or multi-)phasic, many of them showed superconductivity well above 77 K⁵⁴. By comparing the X-ray diffraction patterns of these compositions with the X-ray diffraction pattern of $YBa_2Cu_3O_7$, it was found⁵⁴ by the second week of March 1987 that the phase responsible for superconductivity around 90 K was $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-\delta}$; it was also shown that this phase was probably a minor component in the $Y_{1.5}Ba_{0.5}CuO_4$ composition of Wu *et al.*⁴⁵. Superconducting $YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-\delta}$ was soon shown to be orthorhombic and was characterised by resistivity, AC susceptibility and thermopower measurements^{54,55}.

$YBa_2Cu_3O_{7-\delta}$ prepared in oxygen, air and nitrogen showed different electrical properties. The oxide prepared in pure N_2 atmosphere had a δ value close to unity and was tetragonal. The composition of the oxide prepared in air was close to $YBa_2Cu_3O_{6.7}$ while that prepared in oxygen showed $\delta \approx 0.0$; the latter (stoichiometric) composition showed zero-resistance at a slightly higher

Fig. 7. Resistivity data of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ annealed in oxygen ($\delta \approx 0.0$), in air ($\delta \approx 0.3$) and in nitrogen ($\delta \approx 1.0$).

temperature (Fig. 7). Samples with $\delta = 0.50$ and 1.0 are both insulating (Fig. 7); both possess tetragonal structures. It is noteworthy that the resistivity values of the superconducting samples in the normal state correspond closely to the minimum metallic conductivity of Mott. We generally find that in these oxides, only those with marginal metallicity (in the borderline of metal-insulator transition) exhibit high T_c superconductivity. When $\delta = 0.0 - 0.25$, T_c is $\sim 95 \pm 5$ K; when $\delta = 0.3 - 0.6$, T_c is $40 - 60$ K, indicating a change in the nature of superconductivity with δ .

One of the curious features of superconducting $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ is the presence of banded patterns in the bright-field electron microscopic images⁵⁶. The bands appear uniformly and are generally a few hundred angstroms in width. Such bands do not appear in the nonsuperconducting compositions prepared in a nitrogen atmosphere. The banded patterns could arise from different orientations of the $(\text{CuO}_2)_\infty$ planes⁵⁷ formed by the CuO_4 square-planar groups (Fig. 8), but it is also plausible that it is due to the intergrowth of metallic and insulating phases as considered by us earlier⁵². Phase separation of the metallic and insulating phases at the metal-insulator transition is known. Since these

Fig. 8. Structures of (a) $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ and (b) $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_6$. Notice the absence of the $(\text{CuO})_\infty$ chains in (b).

oxides in the normal state are at the borderline of the metal-insulator transition, it is indeed possible that domains of the two phases intergrow⁵⁸. The presence of such alternating metallic and insulating domains could favour superconductivity. It is however difficult to understand such macrostructural features in terms of the microstructure. The insulating and the metallic compositions would have different compositions of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ (possibly $\delta \approx 0.5 - 1.0$ and $0.0 - 0.5$, respectively) and also different structures (tetragonal and orthorhombic, respectively). The middle layer of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ consists of $\text{Cu}-\text{O}-\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ chains or more correctly, corner-linked CuO_4 units (Fig. 8). When $\delta \approx 1.0$, there would be no $\text{Cu}-\text{O}-\text{Cu}-\text{O}$ chains or CuO_4 units⁵⁹; instead, there would be CuO_2 units along the c-axis⁶⁰ with the Cu atoms of the middle layer making use of the oxygens of the BaO layers (Fig. 6). If there are domains of two such compositions, then what does the 'average' structure determined by neutron diffraction correspond to? Or, is it possible that the twins or domains consist of the stoichiometric oxide, with only a 'minor' filament of an oxygen-rich composition between the bands or domains? This indeed appears to be the case. If compositional changes occur even more frequently, then we would have to say that the variation is within a narrow range of δ . The structures shown in Fig. 8 explain how Y (or any other rare earth ion) has little role to play in the superconductivity⁶¹, but underscores the seminal role of oxygen⁶¹⁻⁶⁴. In understanding the role of oxygen three factors are to be considered: stoichiometry, structure and disorder.

Infrared spectra: We have studied the infrared spectra of $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CuO}_4$ and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ in detail^{60, 62, 61, 62}. Infrared spectra of $\text{La}_{2-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CuO}_4$ recorded at 300 K show a high frequency band at 687 cm^{-1} besides two bands around 510 and 400 cm^{-1} when $x = 0.0 - 0.05$. When $x \geq 0.075$, the high frequency band at 680 cm^{-1} disappears but

the other two bands remain. At this composition, the room-temperature structure changes to tetragonal and the oxide shows superconductivity at low temperatures. $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.4}$ which is tetragonal and nonsuperconducting shows intense bands around 636, 580 and 380 cm^{-1} . $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ which is orthorhombic and superconducting does not show these bands with high intensity. The air-heated sample ($\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.7}$) also shows the bands with low intensity.

Photoemission and other studies : Photoemission studies^{6,3,64} of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CuO}_4$ and $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ have shown that the $\text{O}(1s)$ spectrum can only be understood if it is treated as consisting of three Gaussians with maxima at 529, 531 and 533 eV. The 529 eV peak is due to the oxide ion while the 531 eV peak is due to O^{-1} , CO_3^{2-} or OH^- . The most important feature is that at 533 eV, ascribed to a peroxide-like species which develops in intensity as the temperature is lowered (Fig. 9). This is considered to be due to the formation of holes on oxygen and the subsequent pairing of the holes forming O_2^{2-} species. Accompanying the increased

Fig. 9. Temperature-variation of the 529 and 533 eV features of $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$ due to O^{2-} and O_2^{2-} species and of the intensity at 12 eV in the HeII spectrum. Inset shows the $\text{O}(1s)$ at 80 K as three Gaussians.

formation of the O_2^{2-} species, we see an increase in the proportion of Cu^{1+} species (relative to Cu^{2+} species) in the $\text{Cu}(\text{LVV})$ Auger spectra. The $\text{Cu}(2p)$ spectra also show the presence of the Cu^{1+} species.

We believe that Cu^{1+} is formed by the reduction of Cu^{2+} by the electrons released on the formation of O_2^{2-} from O^{2-} . Resonating $\text{O}-\text{O}$ bonds formed by the pairing of holes in the $\text{O}(2p)$ valence band may indeed be playing a crucial role in the production of the Cooper pairs.

Concluding remarks :

We have been investigating $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{7-\delta}$ carefully as a function of δ by employing TGA, diffraction, infrared spectroscopy, Raman spectroscopy etc. We are also examining the energetics of intercalation of oxygen in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_6$. One of the curious facts about these high-temperature oxide superconductors is that the Cu^{3+} ion has not been seen in X-ray photoelectron spectra. The absence of Cu^{3+} is not particularly liked by some theoreticians, but it is important to develop models based on the presence of Cu^{1+} and O_2^{2-} ions especially in $\text{YBa}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_7$.

We have attempted synthesising the known high- T_c superconductors by other methods, such as the precursor route⁶⁵, but have not found any significant changes in properties. We have prepared several other copper oxides of La, Y, Ba etc., including those of the general formulae $\text{A}_{n+1}\text{B}_n\text{O}_{3n+1}$ (where, $\text{A}=\text{La}, \text{Y}, \text{Ba}$ etc.), $\text{La}_{8-x}\text{Ba}_{3+x}(\text{Sr}_{3+x})\text{Cu}_6\text{O}_{14-5}$ and $\text{Y}_n\text{Ba}_{n-m}\text{Cu}_m\text{O}_{(3n+1)-\delta}$, but have not yet found real high T_c in them. Some of the oxides show resistivity drops at high temperatures (even around 300 K), but are not stable. Measurements of these oxides as well as efforts to prepare stable materials especially those with lanthanum are now in progress. Experiments are also going on to understand fully the role of oxygen (holes in the oxygen $2p$ valence band). The exact role of oxygen in the absorption of electromagnetic radiation over a wide range of frequencies⁶⁶ is yet to be understood.

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